

Table 1. Ordinal logistic regression model which explore associations between patients' rating of the quality of a consultation and patients' characteristics, experiences of care, and self-reported health measures.

	Covariate	OR	CI
Sociodemographic	Sex (1: Women)	0.995	0.676 — 1.463
	Age	1.001	0.987 — 1.015
	Employment status (1: With a paid job)	0.872	0.556 — 1.368
	Log-income	0.987	0.750 — 1.301
Experiences of care measures	Doctor spent enough time in consultation (1: Yes)	7.457 ***	3.236 — 17.180
	Doctor provided easy to understand explanations (1: Yes)	3.079 *	1.247 — 7.605
	Doctor gave the opportunity to ask questions or raise concerns (1: Yes)	4.420 ***	1.877 — 10.408
	Doctor involved the patient in decision making about care (1: Yes)	5.306 ***	2.684 — 10.490
	Waiting time for an appointment (Baseline: Less than a day)		
	Between 2 - 7 days	0.890	0.516 — 1.534
	Between 8 - 30 days	0.685	0.379 — 1.236
	More than a month	0.680	0.361 — 1.279
	Waiting time at the doctor's office (Baseline: Less than 15 minutes)		
	Between 15 - 30 minutes	0.971	0.584 — 1.614
	Between 30 - 60 minutes	0.409 **	0.227 — 0.737
	More than an hour	0.474 **	0.286 — 0.788
	Health-related quality of life	EQ - VAS	0.998
Self-reported health status (Baseline: Very good)			
Good		0.235 **	0.094 — 0.587
Fair		0.258 **	0.096 — 0.694
Bad / Very bad		0.363	0.096 — 1.366
Happiness		1.051	0.955 — 1.157
Health care provider	Health care provider (Baseline: GP)		
	Specialist in a public facility	1.085	0.647 — 1.819
	Specialist in a private facility	1.422	0.732 — 2.762
	Allied Health Professional	1.281	0.339 — 4.835
	Last appointment (Baseline: Less 1 month)		
	1-3 months	0.966	0.610 — 1.530
	3-6 months	0.602	0.334 — 1.084
	6-12 months	0.586	0.336 — 1.023
	Log pseudolikelihood		- 491.134
	N		465

p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001.

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